

An Overview of Autonomous Vehicle Sensor

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Abstract- This work is the structure of an autonomous driving system. This paper aims to determine the current state of autonomous vehicles, their potential impacts, and the necessary preparation for smart urban mobility. Autonomous refers to the movement or the work done on its own. Autonomous driving systems are divided into several ways, such as Autonomous under- water vehicles, Autonomous airborne vehicles, and Autonomous land vehicles. The potential benefits of lane autonomous vehicles are to describe the importance of navigation algorithms, speed control methods, adoption factors, and the increased infrastruc- ture needs for Connected autonomous vehicles' integration. The major key elements are based on sensors, navigation, radar, planning techniques, communication, and software. The results of this research have important implications for future research and the framework of autonomous vehicle technologies in road trans- portation. **Index Terms**—autonomous driving, sensor, RADAR, navigation, software.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In the world of advancement and developing technology autonomous vehicles are one of the major growing innovations. Autonomous refers to an auto-driving vehicle that operates independently. Park shuttle is the first autonomous vehicle used to pick up the member from one station to the other. It was invented in 1997 in the Netherlands. Subsequently, there was a drastic enhancement in AV technology. One notable invention in Advanced Vehicle Systems (AVS) is the development of au- tonomous vehicles or self-driving cars. They have the potential to revolutionize transportation by increasing safety, efficiency, and accessibility. It's an exciting advancement in the world of transportation technology. To clear and create a smart traffic- free environment, autonomous vehicles use cloud computing and big data analysis to combine the networks in urban areas.

The primary concept of AV is to replace the manual driver with self-driving mobiles. Autonomous vehicles support features like environment sensing, internet connecting, consenting the traffic rules, self-navigation, quick decision-making, ensuring pedestrian and passenger safety, parking, etc

Safety and security

On noticing recent days, issues like prone to errors leading to numerous accidents due to anonymous attacks, SQL injection attacks, DDoS, and cyber attacks are increasing gradually. To reduce the attack and enhance security and storage systems. The utilization of blockchain is being applied to autonomous vehicles. [11]According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 1.5L people died due to road accidents. To reduce it, several sensors and devices are being

used in vehicles (Vehicle speed sensor, Parking sensor, Throttle posi- tion sensor, Engine speed sensor, Object detection). Research- based on combining both traffic systems and AV technology to reduce road accidents is in progress. In autonomous vehicles detection of human activities and the movement of vehicles are differentiated in a set of data, so that the risk of being injured is less.

Overview

The overview of this section is to understand the concept of self-driving vehicles, their uses, and their merits and demerits. The major priority given to the AV is based on its increased safety, efficiency, and accessibility. Even though there are some challenges such as susceptibility to errors and cyber attacks, enhancement steps are in progress to overcome those challenges using TUM software and blockchain technology. In the upcoming section, we are going to discuss the sen- sors that are used, the type of navigation, and how we are connecting the data set between the software and hardware. As the technology progresses, future survey papers coul

Fig. 1. sensor used

benefit from a more hands-on approach, showcasing real-world applications and user evaluations to bridge the gap between theory and practice. In this paper, we Embark through the intricate realms of several major IOT technologies used in it (Sensors, GPS and GNSS, Inertial Measurement Units, Computer Vision, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), Navigation(RADAR, LIDAR, camera, root planning), High-Performance Computing, Control Systems, Communication systems, Redundancy, and Safety Systems). In the rest of the survey paper, Section II reviews every software device of an autonomous vehicle and its detailed description. Section III is an overview of the functions and planning of this survey. Section IV sets the seal on this survey with our conclusions.

II. ELEMENTS

The Sensor is one of the common seeing devices nowadays From entering a room to exit a car's door. Sensor-based technologies are transforming the way people connect and work in the workplace, utilizing intelligent sensors to build up productivity and performance. Sensors detect differences in the surroundings, collect the data, and react to the given data. The emissions of IR rays from a sensor that senses the environment act. There are various sensors for different parameters Situation such as temperature, pressure, humidity, light, and motion, among others. The combination of hardware and software technology enhances the transportation system and roadways [12], [10]. There are six major sensor devices, as shown in Fig 1. This key part of the autonomous vehicle is its sensor which is mentioned above. The sensor in the vehicle collects all the information from the sensor and sends it to the processing unit then the control changes according to it - steer, brake, and speed of the vehicle.

Imu Sensor

Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors that contain gyroscopes and Accelerometer. The IMU sensor is a measuring

Fig. 2. uno sensor wave

unit sensor that takes note of the change in the velocity and movement. There are certain drawbacks are there in gyroscope sensors. The integrated slope angle of the gyroscope data has a deviation over a certain period. So

gyroscope is used for the short term. Whereas the accelerometer is useful for the long-term data hold. IMU integrates accelerometer and gyroscope sensors to estimate speed, position, and orientation over time, [6] [8]. The main use of the IMU sensor is, that it gives precise information on the measured distance and the angular movement. Accelerometers are one of the alternatives to the IMU sensor. The Accelerometers couldn't detect both the angle and motion movement. The IMU sensor is more likely to get more preference [7], [13].

Sonar

A Sonar sensor is a digital sensor that transfers the data digitally. The sonar sensor is also known as an ultrasonic sensor. The sensor has two signal faces as shown in Fig 2 The transmitter sends the signal of UV Rays and the ray hits the object reflecting it,, and the reflected ray is detected by the reserver. The ray is usually 40KHz. The experimental structure of the

system working: There are two ultrasonic sensors are placed on the front and back of the car. The distance between the car and the object is 3.2 meters, and the transmitter and receiver of the sensors point to the object. The two sensors are arranged opposite to each other. The distance between the two sensors is set close to each other to prevent two vehicles from being detected at the same time. Understand the data collection process. The Arduino triggers sensor 1 to start measuring the distance to the nearest object and then stores the results in temporary memory. There is a delay before the Arduino does the same for sensor 2 [28], [1]. The measurements from Sensor 1 and Sensor 2 are then saved to the SD card along with the date and time of data collection. The measurement process is then repeated in a loop. So when the object is nearer to the car there is an indication sent to the car. Most commonly this sensor is used in the car parking system. The advancement in technology of the AV includes this where the movement of the vehicle is being calculated. The current AV uses the ultrasonic sensor to track the distance between the car in front and the car in back to take any further movement of the vehicle. With the advancement in technology, the ultrasonic sensor can be

Fig. 3. GPS-guided vehicle

replaced with Optical-based sensing technologies [16]. The Optical-based sensing technologies have a camera and LiDAR

sensor which allows them to give precise measurements and LiDAR is most commonly utilized in the mapping of cars.

Navigation

Navigation is the ability of a vehicle to determine your location and plan a path to reach your destination. It involves a combination of technologies and algorithms to enable vehicles to think in a particular way about their environment, planning the route and reaching their destination safely. The key components involved in navigation are Sensors, Perception, Localization, Mapping, path planning, Control, LIDAR, RADAR, Machine learning, and AI. Autonomous vehicles drive themselves with these virtual technologies with the help of super smart robot pilots [2].

Gps Navigation: GPS (Global Positioning System) navigation is a technology that allows users to determine their location and navigate from one point to another using satellite signals. It depends on a network of satellites orbiting the Earth that transmit signals to GPS receivers, such as those found in smartphones, car navigation systems, or standard GPS devices. The working of GPS Navigation is based on satellite Signals, triangulation, position calculation, navigation planning, and backup systems.

Satellite signal-GPS navigation system receives signals from the network of satellites orbiting the earth. These satellites transmit signals containing information exact location and time. Triangulation-The GPS tracker calculates distance from at least three satellites by measuring the time it takes the signal to travel to its receiver. By knowing the location and time of satellites the receiver can triangulate the position on Earth. Position calculation- It is calculated using the position of different satellites, along with their positions they can able to calculate the latitude, longitude, and sometimes altitude. Backup systems- Having a backup system for GPS navigation is mandatory, especially in case of technology failure and signal disruptions. Some backup methods include physical mapping and compasses [4].

Beacon Navigation Method: Beacon navigation is the effective method for autonomous vehicles particularly in environments where GPS is not available Here is how Beacon

navigation works. The working of the beacon navigation system includes beacon deployment, Signal encoding, localization, etc... Beacon deployment- These emit a signal that can be detected by the autonomous vehicle. Signal encoding- Each beacon emits a unique signal that the autonomous vehicle can recognize. This could be a specific frequency, a unique code, or any other form of signal encoding. V2X Communication method is the key method used in autonomous vehicle navigation, enabling them to communicate with other vehicles' infrastructure, pedestrians, and other connected devices. This method includes Vehicle to vehicle communication, vehicle-to-pedestrian communication, vehicle-to-network communication etc [20], [9].

Theorem

In the context of autonomous vehicle navigation, theorems from the fields of mathematics and computer science may be applied. Several principles and theorems are commonly utilized. The theorem used are the Bayesian Filtering Theorem, Graph Theory, and Shortest Path Algorithms, Control theory, Probability Theory, Game theory, and Information Theory. Bayesian Filtering theorem –This theorem is used in autonomous vehicle navigation to estimate the vehicle's state (eg.. position, velocity) by integrating new sensor data with previous estimates, making navigation more accurate. Probability theory- In autonomous vehicle navigation, probability theory is employed through Bayesian filtering, which updates the vehicle's location and other parameters by incorporating new sensor data with existing estimates. This approach ensures more accurate navigation despite uncertainties in sensor measurements and environmental conditions. These are some of the theorems used in the navigation of autonomous vehicles.

Camera

Cameras are an integral part of the sensor suite in autonomous vehicles, providing visual information for perception, object detection, lane tracking, obstacle detection, navigation, path planning and Driver monitoring. Perception-Cameras capture visual data from the vehicle's surroundings, providing real-time information about the road, traffic, pedestrians, and obstacles. Object detection-Computer vision algo-

Fig. 4. camera-based perception

Fig. 5. Flowchart-obstacle detection algorithm

gorithms analyze camera images to detect and classify objects such as vehicles, pedestrians, cyclists, traffic signs, and lane markings. Obstacle detection- Cameras identify obstacles in the vehicle's path and enable collision avoidance action by detecting and tracking moving objects and stationary obstacles. Cameras are essential components of the sensor suite in autonomous vehicles, providing valuable visual information for perception, decision-making, and safe navigation in diverse driving conditions [2].

RADAR

Radar is a sensory input technology that is crucial to an advanced driver-assistance system (ADAS) and an autonomous driving (AD) system. A radar is a mechanism that spots an object, obstacle, etc., that is found near the vehicles, using radio waves. Radar systems habitually consist of one or more radar units deliberately placed on the vehicle, ordinarily mounted on the front, sides, and rear [29]. An overview of the factors and features of radar systems in an AV is an antenna, transmitter, receiver, single processing unit, control interface, integration with perception and decision-making systems. RADAR sensors in AV play an indispensable role in contributing reliable and robust perception capabilities,

particularly in rigorous environmental conditions such as fog, mist, haze, adverse weather, and diverse lighting atmospheres.

Fig. 6. obstacle sensing

They endorse other sensors like cameras and LiDAR and provide erratic efficiencies such as long-range sensing, all-weather performance, and robustness against hindrances. Innovation in radar technology is rooted in the 'Telemobiloscope' an entry-level radar particularly designed for collision avoidance on ships. It makes use of radio waves to detect the object and unfavorable climatic conditions. Over time, the evaluation of radar technology has been marked by relevant improvements in performance. The upgradation of the sensor starts from the solid-state radar system transition to the vacuum tube designs [24]. The further development and evolution of radar reaches digital signal processing, automotive radar, and remote sensing. Now it focuses on areas like cognitive, quantum, and urban air mobility radar systems. The advancement of radar technologies undergoes continuous refinement in semiconductor technologies, signal process technologies, and system integration. Radar senses objects and unfavorable environments through the transmission and reception of radio waves [22] [17]. The Radar object detection process begins with the waves emitted by the environment being captured by the transmitter using radio wave technology. The transmitted waves then probate through space at the speed of light through propagation. Waves encounter the object and amount of reflection, then the antenna receives the reflected waves with any other signals in the atmosphere. Then the signal processing is done using frequency-domain analysis to detect objects, range, and target. Radar data processing for detecting the front vehicle. Get into further details about how radar senses the front vehicle while it is moving on the road. In AV radar operates mostly at 77 GHz, and the frequency shifted to 79 GHz. It reveals the algorithm to recognize a front vehicle using output signals of the radar. It further implements the details about

Delphi ESR radar and CAN network. On highways, vehicles are detected by radar depth association. In places

like highways, we are not able to put a hand signal for any reason. In AV vehicles, the radar senses the vehicle in all dimensions. It tries to provide the 3D position of the vehicle using radar and camera. Fig [6] shows the exact version of the distance measuring between vehicles in all dimensions [25]. It reveals detailed information about mm waves radar. It gives an exact clear image from radar-like object identification. The main ideology in this approach detects the difference between pedestrian and vehicle [30]. The goal of this experiment is to show how many sensors that arise over the period. From solid-state sensors to 5G radar to make an AV with speed and accuracy radar plays a huge role in AV. It is also responsible for speed detection, measuring the distance between vehicles, and making a difference between pedestrians and vehicles.

H.LiDAR

The light-detecting and ranging remote sensing (LIDAR) method uses light rays in the form of pulsed lasers to compute the range between resolution maps and to detect obstacles, pedestrians, and vehicles. LIDAR exudes rapid pulses of laser light on various vectors to spot obstacles, then the laser attains any object the laser pulse reflects on the LIDAR. LIDAR estimates the reflected light timing and identifies the distance of the object. Point clouds produce information about the time, distance, and location of the object detected. Object classification occurs using point cloud data, which analyses whether the object is a vehicle or any pedestrian. By using mapping and obstacle avoidance processes, the LIDAR detects speed, accuracy, and navigation safety.

The YOLOx technique provides 98.45 percent clarity in the object detection process. However, the LIDAR technique provides only a 95.35 percent precision value for object detection [27]. It provides details about the power consumption and use of laser diode LIDAR to detect a long-distance object while driving AV [15]. The consistency and the acquired distance map are essential to make accurate obstacle detection [3].

Planning System

This comprehensive review focuses on the Autonomous vehicles planning system. The Planning system is taking a core segment in AV to operate vehicles safely and provide accuracy. There are so many planning systems present in the AV world such as behavioral planning, motion planning, route planning, etc. In real-time experiments, every planning plays a various role in AV industries. Behavioral planning took part in making high-level decisions about the vehicle's actions based on the atmosphere and other vehicles' motion. This planning provides a decision, scenario planning, and policy execution of the vehicle in any unfavourable situation. Motion planning mainly focuses on path planning, trajectory optimization, and obstacle avoidance. Route planning took part in map-based navigation, traffic management, and waypoint selection. The Planning system operates under various techniques like model predictive control (MPC), Dijkstra algorithm, and

reinforcement learning. These techniques give a way to make decisions and provide comfort to the passengers. A Constrained Dijkstra approach

Fig. 7. Recognizing challenges

[26] for optimal path-planning missions is proposed. Fig [7] shows vehicle may change the lane while driving at high speed or be able to find an obstacle in a mid-way [14] integrated safe trajectory planning system is evolved for the safe and secure landing of AV system. Dynamic motion planning [32] this approach provides details about AV navigation without GPS and unmanned driving.

Fusion Of Sensor

Whether you realize it or not, robots are a part of your life. You pick up your online order from the warehouse and deliver it safely to your home. You vacuum the floors in your home. They build cars, equipment, and items to make your life more efficient and affordable. The primary concept of all this working concept is sensors from basic ultrasonic to LiDAR sensors. Each sensor in the car can't give the signal directly to the brake or the movement of the vehicle which may cause trouble due to multiple information at the different or same time. The main objective is to perform all the sensors at the right time at the correct place is known as a fusion sensor. The fusion sensors works of the car's multiple sensor at the same time to detect different objects at the same time and the distance as shown in Fig[8].

PRESCRIPTION Lidar radar imu camera fusion
 sensor
 angle
 distance
 velocity
 obstacle
 weather\light

method has some complications in speed and shift control optimization, scholars proposed back-stepping-based neural network control for the synchronous reluctance of motors. The systematic, recursive design approach used in the nonlinear control system which is used to break the complex, nonlinear control problems into simpler sub-problems is identified as backstepping.

Fig. 8. control according to sensor

The sensor like a camera sensor has the disadvantage of sensing the object of its work in dense fog, heavy rain, and sun glare and the radar lacks efficient and accurate image processing where this sensor fusion combines all the information of multiple sensors and combine them give the precise information about the environment [21].

There are five primary steps:

Involved Data Integration, Sensor Calibration, Data Synchronization, Data Synchronization, Sensor Fusion Algorithms, and Decision Making. Collecting the info from all the sensors LiDAR, camera sensor, ultrasonic sensors, GPS, and inertial measurement units (IMUs).

The present sensor is at the standard position before any futher movement of the vehicle.

- The data sets from different sensors are collaboration according to the environment.
- The understanding of the given set of data according to the environment.
- Deciding on the movement of the vehicle.

Kcontrol Of An Autonomous Vehicle

Autonomous vehicles received more and more attention in recent days, with the help of Artificial Intelligence. The control modules majorly involve the perception of the environment, positioning, decision planning, and control execution. Fields like industry, agriculture, and the military are framing a huge application for AVs. In the field of AVs, path-tracking control has become the interest of present researchers. Many scholars consider that adaptive fuzzy control methods have the characteristics of robustness and easy to realize. Path tracking problems in four-wheelers are solved by Multi- model predictive control (MPC). Since this

Fig. 9. sensor accuracy

PRESCRIPTION	LiDAR	radar	imu	camera	fusion sensor
angle					
distance					
velocity					
obstacle					
weather\light					

Reclaimed parts: According to vehicle kinematics information, to track path control, preview distance heading angle deviation and vehicle position deviation are used as the basis of controller design. The most popular path-tracking control method among the existing methods is the PID method. Even though this method has the advantages of simplicity and engineering applications, it has the problem of poor versatility. One of the classical optimal control methods used in path tracking control is the LQR optimal control method. To minimize the lateral path tracking deviation feedforward-feedback steering controller which uses the vehicle center of percussion as a reference point. The vehicle control system consists of various kinds of sensors, controllers, and actuators. AVS uses various kinds of sensors that help to make decisions and navigate safely. Well-known sensors used in AVs are LiDAR, RADAR, cameras, ultrasonic sensors, GPS, IMU, wheel encoders, in- frared sensors, and microphones. To produce more accurate, reliable, and comprehensive information, the data of individual sensors are integrated and form an integrated multiple sensors network, which is recognized as sensor fusion. The control of these sensors is majorly applicable in AVs.

MRAC: The control strategy and Model Reference Adaptive Control (MRAC) in literature are compared with each other, to adjust its adaptability, optimize its performance, handle its robustness, and implement its complexity. MRAC is an adaptive control system where the controller adapts its parameters in real time to ensure system output. In uncer- tain environments, MRAC works dynamically for application suitability. This comparison also leads to finding new ad-

vancements and developments in control theory. To verify the effectiveness of the event-triggered control, hardware in-loop tests are performed. By using this test, we can be able to stimulate real-world scenarios as it is safe, cost-effective, and comprehensive for autonomous vehicles.

Literature

Sensors play a crucial role in Av, allowing the vehicle to observe and analyze the environment and make decisions. The placement of sensors is strategically placed around the vehicle

TABLE I SENSOR PROPERTIES

SENSOR	description	frequency	digital/analog sensor	Distance Rnge	example
camera sensor	the camera sensor used in autonomous vehicle to assist in the detection of moving object	350-1000(nm)	Analog	high	monocular vision camera
gnss sensor	To find the location of the vehicle using satellites	1200-1600 (MHz)	Digital	medium	GPS, GLONASS AND QZSS Satellites
sonar sensor	To detect object near it by using ultrasonic wave	30-500(KHz)	Both analog and digital	low	ultrasonic ,bosch ultrasonic and maxbotix ultrasonic sensor
gps sensor	The GPS system in the car utilize to locate the real time location	1176-1575(MHz)	Both digital and analog	low	Novatel, Trimble and septentrio
LiDAR sensor	It create a environment by using laser pules	1-100(Hz)	Analog	low	quanergy, luminar and velodyne
radar sensor	using radar we can determine the size and range of the object	5-130(GHz)	Analog	high	long range radar and millimeter range radar

providing a clear vision all around the vehicle (4-ultrasonic radar front, back, left, and right/360° LiDAR on top/infrared camera facing front /). Data Acquisition captures the data of each sensor and system to enable the vehicle to perceive its environment and make decisions Sensor.

Calibration is a crucial process in ensuring that all sensors are aligned properly and provide accurate data. This process involves adjusting the sensors to correct for any misalignments or discrepancies in orientation, positioning, and timing.

Sensor synchronization the process ensures that data from different sensors is synchronized in time. Time stamps are used to align data from various sensors so that they represent the same moment in time. This is important for accurate sensor fusion.

Sensor fusion is the process of combining data from multiple sensors to create a comprehensive view of the environment. From raw sensor data for integration and analysis, the given

information by the sensor and the action are recorded in Processing.

The mapping of the vehicle holds an important role in locate the current and upcoming prediction location. SLAM techniques are used to update the vehicle’s map of the surroundings and keep track of its location within that map. Most commonly the SLAM is used for dynamic environments where the vehicle may not have access to pre-existing maps.

Decision and plan building are the most complex and major in all the information stored and playlist and comes to physical action in the vehicle. These algorithms determine the best course of action, such as steering, acceleration, braking, or lane changes.

Software Of Autonomous Vehicles

In enabling various functionalities and operations, software plays a major role. Perception software, localization and mapping software, path planning and control software, decision-making software, communication and connectivity software, safety and redundancy software, user interface and human-machine interface (HMI), and diagnostic and maintenance software are the major key software used in AV.

1) Iov: The perception, decision-making, and control systems, using AI, machine learning, and sensor data to navigate, detect obstacles, and make real-time driving decisions safely

and efficiently are the integration of autonomous vehicle software. The implementation of connected vehicles is linked to the stability of network connections. To explore the surrounding environment, connect various types of traffic lights or other regulatory signals, and realize automatic prompts and avoid dangers IoVs are enabled in the vehicles. To model, analyze, and predict physical aspects, virtual environments are used in various industrial domains.

visual enviroment: The virtual environment is also used in an effective way of treating various mental health issues such as anxiety and trauma. To overcome or complement the inherent limitations of the physical environment, the virtual

environment has been used as a popular system software tester. To resolve the concerns of automakers, the properties of selective sharing and collaboration need to be injected into a specific domain. In the virtual world, some activities are performed by humans, to restrict how participants perform tests CVE-based test framework is used. A set property is carried by each artifact, including its accessibility, published, and certified status. The access to computing and network resources for participants should be checked by admission control.

electronic stability program: For estimating the vehicle numbers, a UAV equipped with eight- an element uniform linear array is used. The electronic stability program (ESP) method is used to propose the best estimation performance. This program is used to maintain vehicle control by applying brakes to the vehicle. It provides skid prevention by adjusting engine power. ESP is integrated with autonomous systems to ensure smooth and safe driving.

• **Effect Of Autonomous Vehicles**

- Autonomous vehicles (AVs) were initially designed with strict safety measures and convenience in mind, such as a time gap of 2 seconds, smooth accelerations and decelerations, and lane changes only under ideal conditions. However, studies have shown that introducing a significant number of AVs with these conservative driving behaviors could lead to increased traffic congestion and reduced capacity on freeways. [19] [23].
- One possible solution is to promote cooperation between vehicles, allowing them to exchange information and make cooperative decisions for safety and overall system efficiency. Dynamic traffic management strategies in coordination with vehicle automation could help address these challenges. Freeway traffic is an ideal scenario to test these strategies due to its controlled nature and the availability of existing technology. One particular strategy could be freeway platooning, where AVs travel in a closely spaced formation at high speeds.
- Research groups have proposed strategies to optimize the formation and modification of platoons, as well as the joining and leaving processes. Advancements in technology will soon make platooning and other advanced traffic management strategies more feasible. However, research in this field is crucial, especially in a mixed-traffic environment where the safety and comfort of human drivers must be ensured while improving overall efficiency.
- The context of driving automation presents an opportunity to implement dynamic traffic management strategies with the necessary technology and coordination. These strategies should be developed

together with vehicle automation and implemented as the AV penetration rate grows. Freeway traffic is likely the first scenario to address, as it represents the most controlled traffic environment and has some required technology available.

• **Functional**

- To make smart decisions sensors like cameras and lidar continuously collect information from the surroundings the detect the speed, position, and trajectory of all nearby vehicles traveling in opposite directions. The algorithms inside the cars analyze all the data given by sensors in real-time. They consider relative distance, speed, and safe options available. The algorithms hold some set of rules to prioritize safety and avoid any collision. The continues in the same lane and safe distance from other vehicles. Algorithms ensure that the car keeps buffer zones and speed control in any accidents. In case of any critical situations, the algorithm decides to control the speed or even to stop the car temporarily. It is similar to humans controlling the car in such situations. The algorithms also adapt to changing conditions. If there is a sudden change in the position of other vehicles the car's smart algorithm can quickly adjust the driving strategy to ensure safety and smooth traffic flow. The car can communicate with other smart vehicles by sharing data this sharing creates a collaborative driving environment allowing people to drive together to avoid conflicts and ensure safe driving. There are no complete autonomous vehicles but partial autonomous vehicles work in this way.

III. SAFETY OF AUTONOMOUS VEHICLE

Safety of autonomous vehicles: Real-time monitoring and diagnostics systems ensure immediate detection and response to potential issues, utilizing health monitoring systems and self-diagnostic tools to track and address problems autonomously. Cybersecurity measures, such as encryption and

intrusion detection systems, protect AVs from cyber threats, while regular software updates patch vulnerabilities and enhance security. Extensive testing in both virtual and real-world environments, including simulations, closed-course testing, and public road testing, ensures the reliability and safety of AV systems [31].

Regulatory compliance with standards such as ISO 26262 for functional safety and SAE J3016 for levels of driving automation, along with adherence to national and local regulations, ensures that AVs meet rigorous safety requirements. Effective human-machine interfaces (HMIs) enhance safety and user experience by providing clear displays, intuitive controls, and emergency override capabilities. Fail-safe mechanisms,

including safe stop procedures, backup power systems, and manual control options, ensure that the vehicle can handle emergencies and malfunctions safely.

Finally, industry collaboration and data sharing promote continuous safety improvements through shared safety databases and the development of best practices and standards by industry consortiums. This comprehensive approach, integrating advanced technology, rigorous testing, robust design principles, and strict regulatory compliance, is essential for developing safe and reliable autonomous vehicles. This provides a cohesive and detailed overview of the key safety aspects of autonomous vehicles [18].

IV. CONCLUSION

The overview of this survey provides the integration of radar, LiDAR, sensors, navigation systems, cameras, communication technology, control mechanisms, and software has paved the way for the assessment of autonomous vehicles. These promotions have not only boosted the safety and efficiency of transportation but also unsealed possibilities for creative implementation across various industries. As we continue to improve and expand upon these technologies, autonomous vehicles are ready to transform the way we move, providing a peek into a future where transit is not just intelligent but also integrated seamlessly. However, trials such as regulatory barriers, ethical contemplation, and technological limitations remain to be addressed. Nevertheless, with current studies and developments, the assurance of autonomous vehicles to reshape our world for the enrich remains progressively approaching to realization.

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